

AN ANALYSIS FROM THE GENDER PERSPECTIVE ABOUT THE (IN)FEASIBILITY OF THE APPLICATION OF SHARED CUSTODY IN CASES OF DOMESTIC VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the feasibility or not of granting shared custody of children in common, between aggressor and victim, in the context of domestic and family violence against women. Based on the view of women as a heterogeneous group, the aim is to analyze the ways in which the Maria da Penha Law changed, or not, the social archetype for crimes involving violence against women in the family environment, what are the stigmas that accompany and how these demands are dealt with when they reach the Police and Judiciary. Still, this research seeks to delimit what are the main consequences for women-mothers who suffer this type of violence and for their children, seriously affecting their development throughout life. Still, the current custody models and the specificities that determine their choice are analyzed, especially taking into account the maxim in our legal system, which determines that custody must be shared whenever possible, being the rule in most cases. In view of this, the objective is to understand whether the shared model is the most appropriate for cases in which there is domestic violence, especially during the validity of a protective measure in favor of women. In this way, hierarchical gender relations are analyzed and how they influence existing family circumstances using the deductive method, starting from the general premise of the legal stipulation of shared custody as a rule in the Civil Code of 2002, for the analysis of cases specific areas marked by violence against women. In the end, it is concluded that custody should not always be granted

to both parents, especially when family dynamics are marked by violence, striving for the best interest of the child and the protection of the woman's physical and mental health.

Keywords : Domestic violence. Shared custody. gender. Families. Feminism.

INTRODUCTION

This article examines the possibility or not of applying the shared custody regime in contexts of domestic violence, considering the consequences that this violence causes to women and their children. In this sense, it is emphasized that the study of hierarchical gender relations is a fundamental element of analysis, considering that family relationships are strongly influenced by the consequences that this hierarchy reproduces in society.

To this end, the research carried out addresses different doctrines and jurisprudence using the deductive method: starting from a general understanding of the emergence and application of shared custody in the Brazilian legal system to reach specific cases related to domestic violence against women and, from In addition, analyze whether the shared regime is the most appropriate.

Thus, the first chapter analyzes the emergence of the Maria da Penha Law, in what context it took place and in what way this law was able, or not, to change the lives of women who go through situations of violence . Still, from the perspective of gender, the ineffectiveness of this Law is discussed with regard to the social archetype constructed for this type of crime, and what needs to change so that women-mothers achieve greater autonomy and security, for themselves and for their children. your children.

In the second chapter, the current custody models and the historical and social process that led to the understanding of shared custody as a rule in the Civil Code of 2002 are analyzed. For this, the role of women in the family over the years and how the This function has always been related to care and mothering, while men were educated to be the providers of the family, without paying much attention to affection. Despite this, with the entry of women into the labor market and their growing search for autonomy, many men decided to act in a more participatory way in caring for their children, postulating the right to a broader coexistence, but still without an equal division of the family. most care duties.

But after all, to what extent can the legal preference for shared custody, supported by the doctrine of full protection, be considered protective in cases of domestic violence against women?

Thus, we discuss the effectiveness of shared custody in situations of domestic violence in the context of the social context in which it occurs, especially with regard to gender roles, investigating whether the application of this institute is a rule that favors social transformation. and also, if it is the most appropriate regime in cases of domestic violence against women. Justified text. Margins: upper and left 3cm, lower and right 2cm. Indent 1.25 cm from the first line, containing the main ideas that guide the text of the article, objectives, research phase, methodological procedures, when applicable, etc.

1. DOMESTIC VIOLENCE AND FAMILIES' RIGHTS

Within the context of institutionalized and legitimized violence in society, there is violence against women, a central element to understand the gender inequalities that are perpetuated until today.

Our society is made up of cultural symbols that add varied representations of the feminine and the masculine, these symbols are endowed with normative concepts, found in religious doctrines, school and laws, as asserted by historian and teacher Joan Scott (1990). In Scott's view, gender is a constitutive element of social relations and the formation of individuals that develop within it, in addition to being the primary way of giving reason to power relations, and cannot be forgotten as a category of analysis.

Thus, the changes that the Maria da Penha Law brought to women will be analyzed below, as well as the harmful consequences that this violence entails for children and adolescents who develop in this reality.

Advances and setbacks of the Maria da Penha Law

Law nº 11.340/06 - Maria da Penha Law (LMP), inspired by the Inter-American Convention to Prevent, Punish and Eradicate Violence against Women - Convention of Belém do Pará, and in the work of feminist NGOs (BANDEIRA, 2009) provided a change of legal action in the treatment of gender violence that occurs in the domestic environment. More than that, it sought to promote a change in social values regarding violence caused by gender within family, domestic and affective relationships.

This legal institute brought important innovations, such as that provided for in Article 30, which refers to the creation of a multidisciplinary team, which operates in the Specialized Courts in order to facilitate the activity of the judge of the judicial branch, the battered woman

and her family members. The law also encourages the work of professionals from other areas, such as psychology and social work, to better treat the victim.

In this context, the Maria da Penha Law exemplifies the main types of violence against women without creating new criminal types, but favors a re-reading of existing types, in addition to ensuring differentiated treatment (positive discrimination) for women, in order to try to make up for gender differences (RÉGIS, 2015). Soon, the concept of domestic violence was expanded to encompass other behaviors that were already quite present in the Family Courts, such as property violence in divorce proceedings with sharing of property, for example.

However, despite some advances, its validity and application were not able to change the popular archetype for this type of problem or to create a really effective protection web for women who suffer violence within their homes, much less for children and adolescents who develop within this family context.

In addition, it appears that the criminal process is also a stigmatizing instrument for the victim, since in the vast majority of cases it does not allow women to participate in the construction of the traditional criminal response. Thus, the woman who reports the aggression is often seen as an unbalanced person, or worse, if she decides to resume the relationship with the author of the violence, she is discredited and ridiculed by those with whom she lives.

In the context of domestic violence, Martha Chamallas (2003) argues that an alternative to thinking about legal responses to this problem is the possibility of recognizing, by the one who narrates, and by the one who conducts the research, the dominant exploratory mechanisms related to gender, race and social class that may be invisible. This is because, behind every case of domestic violence, there is a sexist, racist and patriarchal structure, still very present in our society, in which some men feel entitled to subjugate women to their domain and desires.

In this sense, the role of education is essential, which must begin in the family and extend to formal education. We must teach boys and girls, from an early age, to recognize and respect differences, the ethical and social values of the person and the family. (VARGAS, MACHADO, 2017, p.102)

Thus, although the LMP does not explicitly harm women and proposes some strategies for coping with the problem of domestic and family violence, it has not been able to effectively reduce the incidence of these cases in family dynamics, according to research carried out by Intelligence in Research and Consulting (IPEC)¹³.

¹³According to a survey carried out in February 2021 by IPEC (Intelligence in Research and Consulting), 6% of Brazilian women report having suffered physical aggression from their boyfriend, partner or ex, which is equivalent to 5.3 million women aged 16 or over. more. This vulnerability becomes even more serious when it is verified that the percentage is higher among women aged 35 to 44 years (8%), black and brown (7%) and with

Law 11.340/06 was also not successful in providing escape routes and favoring the fulfillment of full protection for children and adolescents living in contexts of domestic violence, especially when the author of this violence is the parent. Thus, it ended up being up to the Family Courts to face this problem when designating the regime of custody and coexistence of these young people in a vulnerable situation, leading to an unavoidable collision of principles, as will be analyzed throughout this study.

Impacts of Domestic Violence on the development of children and adolescents

The family is considered a basic element of our society, a natural environment for the growth and development of the individual, and for this very reason the Child and Adolescent Statute (ECA) reinforces that children and adolescents must receive protection and assistance in order to develop in a healthy way, fully, prioritizing the family as a determining means for this to happen (SAGIM, 2008).

In this context, it is noteworthy that the notion of family has changed a lot over the years, and may currently mean the “[...] coexistence under the same roof of father/mother, grandmother/grandfather, uncles/aunts, cousins/cousins and/or brothers/sisters; or even ways of living together that involve people united not by ties of civil kinship, but by bonds of friendship [...]” (MENDES, 2016, p.02), for example, being visible the existence of the most varied arrangements relatives.

These changes were due, in part, to feminist movements around the globe that led to the entry of women into the labor market, the facilitation of access to effective contraceptive methods (mainly for white middle-class women), the institution of divorce in Brazil, the legalization of same-sex marriage, among other social advances.

However, even with some progress in the area of families, established intra-family relationships are still strongly marked by the imaginary of the female figure linked almost inseparably to domesticity. Responsibility for raising and caring for children is assigned to women and control of other social/universal spheres is assigned to the male figure. The subordination of women within the family environment often occurs through violence, whether

elementary education (11%). These numbers are compatible with the profile of victims of femicide in the country, which mostly affects women between 30 and 44 years old (41.4% of victims) and with low education, according to data from the Brazilian Public Security Forum.

physical, sexual, psychological, moral and/or patrimonial, that is, whatever the family model, this is still a locus of male *domination*, of “wild power” (FERRAJOLI, 2006).

The violence that seems to be invisible in the eyes of many, including the Family Courts, actually affects not only the woman, but everyone with whom she relates, especially the children. In this context, as Diniz and Angelim (2003, p. 26-27) point out:

Children and adolescents who grow up in contexts of violence often have a series of personal and interpersonal difficulties. The presence of anxiety, fear, depression is common. Learning and behavior disorders may appear - lack of attention, drop in school performance, irritability and aggression with colleagues.

These environments of violence are characterized by the presence of fear, attitudes of objectification of the other and consequent denial of their needs and desires, by deprivation of an affective, economic and/or social nature and, finally, by processes of distortion of subjective reality or interpersonal (BUCHER-MALUSCHKE; ARAÚJO, 2004).

Thus, according to Diniz and Angelim (2003), this process ends up generating feelings of indifference from one member of the family to the other, precarious communication and affective exchanges and the spread of violent and self-destructive behaviors as a means of interaction between family members, as well as these to society.

According to the researchers, it is also worth remembering that people who live in violent environments may have more difficulty in individualizing themselves. Children often play the role of mediators and moderators of aggressiveness between father and mother, seeing themselves forced to assume a position that does not fit them, greatly harming their development, since they are exposed to complaints and violent behavior, whether in speech or in attitudes, from one parent to the other.

The children, in this case, also end up being burdened with the role of caregivers, whether for the mother, who is already weakened by the repeated usurpation of her rights, or for the siblings, who often end up having to “raise themselves alone”, relying on the help only of each other. This place occupied by children and adolescents involved in the family dynamics narrated above is extremely stressful and generates conflicts of loyalty, in which the young person does not know which side to take in a war that has no winners, only victims.

2. ARRANGEMENT OF THE CUSTODY REGIME IN CASES OF DOMESTIC VIOLENCE

The Civil Code of 1916 had a highly repressive and punitive character, determining that in the event of a separation, the children would be under the custody of the “innocent” spouse, that is, it sought to sanction those who “caused” the separation, and in most cases, the blame lay with the wife. As a consequence of this, the old legal system used children as a “prize”, disregarding their interest and objectifying them as a bargaining chip (DIAS, 2021)

This situation changed, in part, with the enactment of Law n° 6.515/77 (Divorce Law) and later with the publication of the 2002 Civil Code, in addition to the changes resulting from the entry of women into the labor market, requiring a new regulation of custody regime.

However, behind this appearance of a modern family, there are still many obstacles to the full realization of the rights of children and adolescents to family life in a healthy and safe environment. In this context, how should the magistrate proceed when the couple's separation is verified the practice of domestic violence against the mother, perpetrated by the parent, when both want custody of the children? This is the question that this chapter tries to answer.

Historical evolution of families and custody regimes

With the Constitution of the Republic, the principle of equality was enshrined, assuring men and women the same rights and duties regarding society and marital, provided for in article 226, § 5, Federal Constitution, which caused significant reflections on family power (DAYS, 2021). Furthermore, the Child and Adolescent Statute gave absolute priority to this particularly vulnerable group, transforming them into subjects of rights.

In this way, considering the formal equality between men and women inaugurated by the Federal Constitution (merely formal equality, the practice is still different for parents), the principle of the best interest of the child, guided by the doctrine of Integral Protection, was increasingly used by of parents who began to demand a greater participation in their children's lives.

This movement inaugurated some achievements for the male gender in the field of families, and why not, in many cases this achievement also belongs to the children, perhaps the most important of which is the publication of Law 11.698/08, which amended the Civil Code establishing shared custody as the preferred model to be followed (Article 1584, § 2, CC).

Thus, the Civil Code, in its article 1,583, provides for two types of custody, unilateral and shared, defining as shared custody that of joint responsibility and exercise of rights and duties by the father and mother who do not live under the same ceiling, concerning family power over children in common. On the other hand, the same article defines unilateral custody as that attributed to only one of the parents, or to someone who replaces him, without necessarily having the loss of family power by the one who does not have custody.

Shared custody is now recommended whenever both parents hold family power and have not explicitly informed that they do not want it. Thus, in shared custody there is the setting of a residence for the children, considered their home of reference, but the parents jointly make decisions regarding the offspring, such as the choice of school where they will study, organization of schedules and routine, choice of complementary activities, etc.

However, for shared custody to be really effective in fulfilling the best interests of the child, the joint participation of parents in the rights and responsibilities over their children's lives is essential, requiring a minimally harmonious coexistence between them, with respect and without violence.

Thus, in cases of domestic violence against women, when the dissolution of the loving union occurs due to the impossibility of maintaining a conjugal life with the aggressor himself, a situation aggravated when there are children in common, the victim/woman/mother finds herself in a delicate dilemma, in view of the imminent risk to the mother and/or children, as will be explained below.

Compulsory application of shared custody: necessity or imprudence?

In Family Courts, disputes over children are common in contexts of various types of violence to which women are victims in the domestic sphere. Still, the criminal response given by the State, in most cases, slow, is just one of the spheres in which this violence is faced, so that it is possible and necessary to integrate the criminal sphere and its protective instruments with other areas of Law, among these, Family Law.

In the same way that the protective measures determined by the Maria da Penha Law, such as removing the aggressor from the home and living with the victim, are necessary for the physical and mental integrity of the woman, these measures are also an obstacle to paternal-child coexistence (MARTINS; FUCHS; CURY 2017).

In disputes over the custody of children, issues are raised that must be analyzed beyond the actual care for them, considering that in situations of domestic and family violence, sharing

custody transcends the “desire for care” and reflects an exercise power over the family. Still, the determination of the shared regime can rekindle points of tension between the parents, since it demands constant contact between them for everyday situations (MENDES, 2016)

This is not to say that shared custody is not beneficial, in general, to children, nor that the right of coexistence between parents and children should be hampered in an authoritarian way without due contradiction, which is often confused with the institute from the guard. What is exposed in the present study is that the determination of the regime of shared custody as a rule in the current legal system, established by Law n° 13.058/14 in an imposing way, in some cases, can lead to risk situations for both the mother and the child. offspring.

It should be noted that custody and coexistence are distinct institutes, even if the parent does not have custody of the children, the right to live with them, which is more than simply visiting them, should not be arbitrarily restricted. The paternal-filial coexistence, more than a desire to exercise paternity, is the right of the child, however, in exceptional situations of violence, it must be given with great caution, in an assisted manner and depending on the case, under the supervision of a professional qualified, whether in the area of psychology or social work.

Compulsory determining shared custody in contexts of latent and frequent domestic violence would only pose even more difficulties for the internal organization of families, further impairing the exercise of autonomy of the mother affected by violence, placing her at the mercy of paternal dispositions. This is because, despite the current legal system providing for formal equality, as already explained, social institutions and courts do not meet the needs of these women-mothers in vulnerable situations, whose demands are repeatedly silenced.

According to Simioni (2017), despite several studies demonstrating a change in the traditional model of fatherhood, with a greater interaction of men in the domestic and parental environment, the finding that gender asymmetries persist, with the reproduction of traditional definitions of what would be the role of father and mother, with paternity being more peripheral and less requested. For this very reason, women are the main claimants in the family courts, often taking care of their children without the support of their ex-partners, explains the author.

As women are the main plaintiffs in the Family Courts, it is not surprising that there are reports of domestic and intra-family violence in the hearings and processes that are carried out in these courts, which are often the main reason that lead them to file a lawsuit (SIMIIONI, 2017).

Thus, for women, the urgent protective measure is intended to guarantee, in theory, the intervention of the State with the restriction of some rights of the parent, including the

prohibition of approaching and contacting the victim, extended to the family members of the victim. victim, as determined by article 19, paragraph 3 of the Maria da Penha Law.

Thus, the scope of protective measures in family processes generates a conflict of interests between the right to physical and mental health of the abused woman and the right to exercise custody on the part of the father. Many magistrates who preside over the hearings in the family courts understand that the protective measure does not prevent either the right to coexistence or the exercise of shared custody, as long as the protective measure is directed only at the mother, while in the specialized courts of domestic violence the understanding is distinct, prevailing the interest of women (SIMIIONI, 2017).

A problem that arises in this context, then, is the lack of communication between these civil and criminal spheres, causing divergence of understanding and legal uncertainty for the parties involved.

What happens is that several times, without this correspondence between the spheres, the family court can stipulate a preliminary custody regime while there is a protective measure in favor of the child's mother or some precautionary measure in favor of the children.

In this area, in-depth knowledge of the psychology of human behavior is not necessary to predict that the success of shared custody depends on the active participation of both parents in decisions surrounding the children's lives, requiring a minimally harmonious and peaceful coexistence between the parents .

It should be noted that the parents' relationship is not expected to be absolutely peaceful or that shared custody is only determined when both parents so wish, since, if that were the case, the rule would be unilateral custody to one of the parents. What is discussed here is that in cases where there is violence against women, breaking the limit of mere misunderstandings common to married life, the custody and coexistence regime established in the family courts must be analyzed with great caution, and in in many cases, the unilateral custody regime is determined.

In this way, the restriction on the right to family life must be carefully analyzed, with the attentive action of professionals who work in the Domestic Violence Courts so that the Maria da Penha Law is correctly applied. Also, for the custody and coexistence regime to be stipulated fairly and without presenting risks to the safety of mother and children, there must be effective communication between the family and criminal courts, avoiding the existence of conflicting decisions that cause insecurity to all those involved in the conflict.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

When domestic violence coincides with the separation of the couple, passing to the stipulation of the regime of custody and coexistence before the justice system, the existing conflict is amplified, with an evident clash of principles: the right to exercise shared custody by both parents facing the right to maternal security and full protection of children.

In the meantime, there are rare cases in which the solely criminal approach does not put an end to violence, as well as an action exclusively in the civil demand, with the determination of a forced coexistence between the parents to enable the exercise of custody, without considering the context violence, ends up exposing the woman and children to new risks.

Thus, considering that no measure is eternal in law, the general rule of shared custody must be mitigated in cases of domestic violence. Each and every decision must be seriously considered and periodically reassessed, with an effective communication channel between the Family Courts and the Specialized Courts of Domestic and Family Violence, in order to ensure the best interests of the child and adolescent, as well as the safety of the woman-mother who is in a situation of vulnerability.

REFERENCES

BRAZIL, **Law No. 11,340** , of August 7, 2006 . Official Gazette of the Union, Brasilia/DF, 8 Aug. 2006. Available at: < http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2004-2006/2006/lei/111340.htm >. Accessed on February 10, 2022.

FLAG, Lourdes. **Three decades of feminist resistance against sexism and female violence in Brazil: 1976 to 2006**. Sociedade & Estado, Rio de Janeiro, v. 24, no. 2, 2009.

BUCHER-MALUSCHKE, J. **Bonding, affectivity and violence: challenges for the family and society**. In: MALUSCHKE, G., BUCHER-MALUSCHKE, J., and HERMANNNS, K. Human rights and violence: challenges for science and practice. Fortress: Konrad Adenauer Foundation and UNIFOR, 2004.

BUENO, Samira; REINACH, Sofia. **Every minute, 25 Brazilians suffer domestic violence**. Available at: < <https://piaui.folha.uol.com.br/cada-minuto-25-brasileiras-sofrem-violencia-domestica> > Accessed on 03/27/2022.

CHAMALLAS, Marha. **Introduction to feminist legal theory**. 2. Ed. New York: Aspen Publishers, 2003.

DIAS, Maria Berenice. **Family Law Handbook** . 14th ed. Juspodium. 2021.

DINIZ, GRS; ANGELIM, F. P - **Domestic violence – Why is it so difficult to deal with it?**

UNESP Journal of Psychology, 2003

FERRAJOLI, Luigi. **Law and reason: theory of criminal guaranteeism** . São Paulo: Revista dos Tribunais, 2006

IBDFAM. **Reflective groups and rehabilitation work with perpetrators of domestic violence** . 2018. Accessed October 12, 2020.

LOBO, Paul. **Civil Law: Families** . 4. Ed. São Paulo: Saraiva, 2011.

MARTINS, Aquiles, FUCHS, Lucas, CURY, Thais. **Child custody in cases of domestic violence against women**. CAAP Magazine | n. 01 | V. XXII. 2017.

MENDES, Soraia da Rosa. **Criminal Justice and Family Justice: Shared Custody and the Protection That Unprotects**. RDU. Porto Alegre. Special Edition, 2016.

OLIVEIRA, André Luiz Pereira. “ **If you stay with our children, I'll kill you!**”: domestic and family violence against women and child custody disputes pending in the Family Courts of Ceilândia/DF. Master's Dissertation by the University of Brasilia, 2015.

REGIS, Mario Luis Delgado. **Patrimonial violence against women in family disputes** . v. 2, 2015.

SAGIM, Mirian Botelho. **Domestic and family violence observed and experienced by children and adolescents in the family environment**. Ribeirão Preto, 2008.

SCOTT, Joan W. **Gender: A Useful Category for Historical Analysis** . Education and Reality, vol. 16, no 2, Porto Alegre, 1990.

SIMIONI, Fabiane. **International Seminar Making Gender 11 13th Women's Worlds Congress**, Florianópolis, 2017.

VARGAS, Ivete Machado; MACHADO, Madgeli Frantz. **Gender Reflective Group: a successful experience for the prevention, care and confrontation of domestic violence against women** . Law readings: domestic and family violence against women / Cornélio Alves; Deyvis de Oliveira Marques (Org.). – Christmas: TJRN, 2017.